

SOCIAL SCIENCES

TEACHING CHALLENGES FOR HANDLING DIFFICULT STUDENTS

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Abstract

School is the most important educational and socialization institution and it creates the first sense of employment for all students. One of the complex challenges is “the handling of difficult students it means the children suffering from psychological difficulties such as SEBD (social-emotional and behavioral problems) The main goal of this study is to shed light on the teachers’ attitudes regarding their skills in the handling of students with psychological difficulties, mostly students diagnosed with SEBD. This is a qualitative study with quantitative elements. Having in mind the conclusions of this study can be said that there are statistically significant differences between teachers’ age, teachers’ gender, and the level of teachers’ training and students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties

Keywords: Pupils with SEBD (social-emotional and behavioral problems); management/handling skills; untrained teachers; trained teachers; male teachers; female teachers

1. Introduction

Nowadays, students with social, emotional, and behavioral problems (SEBD) and those with psychological difficulties have become more than a serious challenging issue not only for young teachers but also for old teachers as well. This problem requires that teachers come up with new teaching strategies for providing positive classroom management for all students including those with SEBD. In recent years, behavior difficulties in schools have increased, teachers seem to be unprepared to deal with the problem and the standard classroom management strategies teachers rely on do not appear to be working. According to Landrum, Tankersley, and Kaufmann (1998), they are more likely to drop out of the education system prematurely than students without SEBD. According to C.E.C.P (1998), “Difficult student misbehaviors, reported by teachers included violation of classroom rules, being truant from school, blaming others for problems, irresponsible behavior, and destruction of property.” according to Cartledge and Talbert Johnson (1996), teachers have been found to perceive students with SEBD as unlikely to be motivated for school work. Traditionally, teachers have dealt with student behaviors that interfere with classroom instruction by using various kinds of negative consequences (e.g., verbal reprimands, time-out, and suspension). A healthy social-emotional environment in school has been shown to reduce SEBD. The process of identification and intervention is a key factor in addressing the special

educational needs of students, including those with SEBD and those with other psychological difficulties.

2. Methodology

1.1 Objective

This study is intended to answer the following research questions:

1- Is there any difference between teachers’ ages as far as concerned their attitudes toward handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties?

2- Is there any difference between teachers’ genders with respect to their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties?

3- Is there any difference between teachers’ training levels with regard to their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties?

Participants

The population of this study was made up of the teachers from two 9-year elementary schools in the city of Permet, more concretely teachers from “Meleq Gostnishti” and “Nonda Bulka” schools. The sample of the study is with convenience, and in total were interviewed, 44 teachers.

1.2 Instrument

This study was quantitative research and was aimed at assessing the level of teachers’ perceptions based on their age, their gender, and level of training in

handling students suffering from SEBD (social-emotional and behavioral problems) and other psychological difficulties. In addition, a questionnaire was used to assess teachers' attitudes regarding their skills to handle students with psychological difficulties, mostly students with SEBD (social-emotional and behavioral problems) and other psychological difficulties.

1.3 Procedure

As I mentioned above the type of this sample was based on convenience sampling, which is useful in getting general ideas about this phenomenon. Confidentiality and anonymity were taken into consideration during the application of the questionnaire.

1.4 Data analysis

The results were analyzed with the SPSS version 21, and the study findings can be more than interesting and can positively contribute to the debate on this issue.

3. Results

3.1. Data analysis through ANOVA.

In this part of the study, has been used ONE WAY ANOVA as one of the most effective methods for analyzing and interpreting the differences between the averages of variables.

Table 1.

ANOVA for the difference between teachers' ages as far as concerned their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties
ANOVA

STUDENTS WITH SEBD AND STUDENTS WITH OTHER PSYCHOLOGICAL DIFFICULTIES					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	169.403	1	169.403	30.371	.000
Within Groups	239.842	43	5.578		
Total	409.244	44			

Table 1 indicates that there is a statistically significant difference between teachers aged 35-40 age and those aged 45-50 age as far as concerned their attitudes

in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties, $F(1,43) = 30.371, P = .000 < .05, (P < \alpha)$.

Fig. 1. Comparison for the mean level of teachers' age as far as concerned their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties

Fig 1 showed that the mean level of teachers aged 35-40 age is $M = 8.75$, whereas the mean level of teachers ranging from 40-50 age is $M = 12.6087$. Based on these results we can see that there is a huge difference in the level of teachers' age as far as concerned their attitudes in the handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties more concretely, Teachers of the age 35-45 years old have lower confidence in their skills to manage students with SEBD and students with other psychological difficulties than teachers of the age 45-50.

Table 2.

ANOVA for the difference between teachers' genders regarding their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties

STUDENTS WITH SEBD AND STUDENTS WITH OTHER PSYCHOLOGICAL DIFFICULTIES					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	135.340	1	135.340	21.247	.000
Within Groups	273.905	43	6.370		
Total	409.244	44			

The table 2 shows that there is a statistically significant difference between male teachers and female teachers with respect to their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties, $F(1, 43) = 21.241, P = .000 < .05, (P < \alpha)$.

Fig. 2. Comparison of the mean level of teachers' gender regarding their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties

Fig 2. indicates that the mean level of male teachers is $M=8.857$, whereas the mean level of female teachers is $M=13.333$, which means that male teachers have lower confidence in their skills to handle students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties than female teachers.

Table 3.

ANOVA for the difference between teachers' training levels about their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	135.340	1	135.340	21.247	.000
Within Groups	273.905	43	6.370		
Total	409.244	44			

The table 3 indicates that there is a statistically significant difference between trained teachers and untrained teachers concerning their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties, $F(1, 43) = 21.241$, $P = .000 < .05$, ($P < \alpha$).

Fig 3. Comparison of the mean level of teachers' training levels regarding their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties

Fig 3. indicates that the mean level of untrained teachers is $M=8.727$, whereas the mean level of trained teachers is $M=12.68$, which means that trained teachers have higher confidence in their skills in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties than untrained teachers.

2. Discussions

The purpose of this study was to shed light on the teachers' attitudes regarding their skills in handling of students with psychological difficulties, mostly students diagnosed with SEBD (social-emotional and behavioral problems) and other psychological difficulties. The sample of the study is with convenience, and in total was interviewed, 44 teachers came from Meleq Gostnishti "and "Nonda Bulka" schools. A questionnaire was used to assess teachers' attitudes regarding their skills in handling students with SEBD and students with other psychological difficulties. For the

data analysis, it was implemented the Statistical Package for Social Sciences. This study was intended to find some scientific responses regarding the research questions below:

1- Is there any difference between teachers' ages as far as concerned their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties?

Regarding the first question was used ANOVA. The table 1 of ANOVA results indicated that there is a statistically significant difference between teachers belonging to 35-40 age and those belonging to 45-50 age as far as concerned their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties, $F(1,43)$

$=30.371$, $P = .000 < .05$, ($P < \alpha$). Graph nr.1 of ANOVA showed that the mean level of teachers belonging to 35-40 age is $M=8.75$, whereas the mean level of teachers belonging to 40-50 age is $M=12.6087$. Based on these results we can see that there is a huge

difference in the level of teachers' age as far as concerned their attitudes in the handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties more concretely, Teachers of the age 35-45 years old have lower confidence in their skills to manage students with SEBD and students with other psychological difficulties than teachers of the age 45-50.

2- Is there any difference between teachers' genders with respect to their attitudes in

ANOVA was employed for the second question. The table Nr.2 of ANOVA results showed that there is a statistically significant difference between male teachers and female teachers with respect to their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties, $F(1, 43) = 21.241$, $P = .000 < .05$, ($P < \alpha$). The graph nr.2 of ANOVA indicated that the mean level of male teachers is $M = 8.857$, whereas the mean level of female teachers is $M = 13.333$, which means that male teachers have lower confidence in their skills to handle students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties than female teachers.

3- Is there any difference between teachers' training levels with regard to their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties?

Regarding the third question, it was used ANOVA. The table 3 of ANOVA results showed that there is a statistically significant difference between trained teachers and untrained teachers with respect to their attitudes in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties, $F(1, 43) = 21.241$, $P = .000 < .05$, ($P < \alpha$). The graph nr.3 of ANOVA indicated that the mean level of untrained teachers is $M = 8.727$, whereas the mean level of trained teachers is $M = 12.68$, which means that trained teachers have higher confidence in their skills in handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties than untrained teachers.

4. Conclusions

To conclude we can say that there was a statistically significant difference between teachers' ages as far as concerned their attitudes toward handling students with SEBD and other psychological difficulties. Teachers of the age 35-45 years old had lower confidence in their skills to manage students with SEBD and students with other psychological difficulties than teachers of the age 45-50. Secondly, there was a statistically significant difference between teachers of different genders. Male teachers had lower-trained teachers were more predisposed to indicate higher confidence in themselves in handling students with SEBD and students with other psychological difficulties confidence in their skills to handle students with SEBD and students with other psychological difficulties than female teachers. There was also a statistically significant difference between trained teachers and untrained teachers. Another interesting finding was that compared to untrained teachers.

BACK MATTER

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Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

Authors contribution

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